

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part X. Adsorption of Water Vapour by Casein and Casein Fractions

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Adsorption isotherms of water vapour by casein and its major fractions obtained at 30° have been analysed by B.E.T., Harkins and Jura and Frankel, Halsey and Hill equations. The values for monolayer capacity as obtained by the first two equations and as read from the knee of the isotherm itself are in good agreement with one another. The mean diameter of casein particles, as calculated from specific surface area value, is in fair agreement with the value obtained by the use of electron microscope as reported in the literature. The correctness of the monolayer capacity is also supported by sudden change in thermodynamic functions, namely, free energy, differential heat and entropy of adsorption. The formation of multimolecular layers at r.v.p.'s ≥ 0.6 is supported by Frankel, Halsey and Hill plots. The water sorbed at r.v.p. < 0.6 does not freeze even at -40°C , and may be taken as held tightly to the surface.

ADSORPTION of water vapour by a variety of proteins¹⁻⁶, including casein⁷⁻¹⁰, has been reported by a number of workers in recent years. A study of water sorption by milk powder¹¹ has also shown that casein picks up moisture, particularly at lower relative vapour pressures, more rapidly than the other constituents. It has been suggested that the sorption proceeds at specific hydrophilic sites^{1,6,9} although opinions differ with regard to chemical groups which constitute such sites¹². The data have also been used for studying genetic variations amongst some of the proteins¹³. The problem is important also from the point of view of storage of casein and other proteins as any water held in excess of monolayer may be available for microbial growth leading to deterioration or even denaturation of the products.

Experimental

Casein was isolated from bovine as well as buffalo milk by the gradual addition of 1 M hydrochloric acid to skim milk, diluted four times with water and kept stirred mechanically all along, till the pH value was lowered to isoelectric point. The precipitate was washed and then separated into α - and

β -fractions, which constitute, amongst themselves, nearly 95% of casein, by taking advantage of their differential solubilities in urea¹⁴. The products were dried over sulphuric acid under vacuum to constant weight, powdered to pass through sieves of different mesh numbers and stored in sealed bottles. Adsorption isotherms of water vapour were determined at 30° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) by the McBain balance technique, taking 0.2 g casein for each experiment and using a quartz fibre spring of 20.6 cm/g sensitivity. The results of various replicates were reproducible within 0.6% of one another. The vapour pressure at each step was raised only after the attainment of equilibrium at the preceding stage.

Results and Discussion

The amount of water sorbed by the particles of unfractionated casein (bovine) passing out of various sieves when brought in equilibrium with different relative vapour pressures of water at 30° are given in Table 1. The time required for the attainment of equilibrium in each case is also given in an appropriate column. It is seen that there is hardly any significant difference in the sorption values of various

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF PARTICLE SIZE ON THE AMOUNT OF WATER ADSORBED ON BOVINE WHOLE CASEIN

Size of particle (mesh no.)	Time of equilibrium (hr.)	Amount of water adsorbed at different relative vapour pressures							
		0.05	0.10	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70
50	4.00	3.50	5.10	6.20	7.20	8.40	9.85	11.50	13.75
100	2.75	3.40	5.00	6.10	7.25	8.45	9.85	11.52	13.70
200	1.50	3.50	5.00	6.25	7.25	8.60	9.90	11.60	13.80
300	1.30	3.52	5.05	6.21	7.30	8.60	9.95	11.60	13.80

aggregates at a given relative vapour pressure inspite of large variations in particle size. There is difference only in the time required for the attainment of equilibrium. The finer the particle the faster the approach of equilibrium. These observations also show, incidentally, that the sorption of water vapour by a lyophilic powder is independent of the size of its aggregates. Each aggregate, after all, is merely an assemblage of several ultimate units, the larger the number of such units, the larger the size of the aggregate. As long as the size of the ultimate units remains the same, there can be no change in the sorption value.

The isotherms on bovine and buffalo caseins and their major fractions are shown in Fig. 1 and 2, respectively. Each isotherm is convex to adsorption

Fig. 1 & 2. Water adsorption isotherms of bovine and buffalo's caseins respectively at 30°.

- Δ—Δ—Δ Whole casein
- X—X—X α-casein
- O—O—O β-casein

axis, shows a knee at about 0.175 relative vapour pressure and is of 'type II' indicating formation of multimolecular layers. The bovine products take up

a little more moisture at a given relative vapour pressure than the corresponding buffalo products. β-casein is seen to be less hydrophilic, in each case, than α-fraction. It appears anomolous, however, that the unfractionated casein is relatively more hydrophilic than either of its major fractions. This may be due to activation of one fraction by the presence of the other through packing of some of the molecules of one fraction into intramolecular spaces of the other, thus presenting a more compact surface to water vapour.

The application of B.E.T. equation to sorption of water vapour by proteins has been questioned by some of the workers^{15,16} on the ground that there may be specific adsorbate-adsorbent interactions on account of the presence of polar groups in proteins. The application of the equation to nitrogen isotherms (78°K), however, has yielded very low values of specific surface area in comparison to the values computed on the basis of particle size obtained from light scattering or ultra microscopic techniques. This appears to be due to inhibiting influence of the polar groups to the sorption of nitrogen. Several workers, therefore, have used, fruitfully water sorption data for estimating specific surface area by applying B.E.T. equation. The B.E.T. plots of $\frac{x}{v(1-x)}$ against x where x is p/p_0 and v is the weight of water adsorbed per 100g of casein, are shown in Fig. 3 and 4 for the bovine and buffaloes' caseins, respectively. It is seen that the plots are linear within 0.05-0.35 relative vapour pressure range, as required by the theory. The value of constant C , is equal to $e^{(E_1-E_L)/RT}$ (where E_1 is the heat of adsorption in the first layer and E_L is the heat of liquifaction of the adsorbate). The values of E_1-E_L and V_m (the amount of adsorbate required to form a monolayer) are reported in Table 2. The specific surface area values, obtained from the respective V_m taking 10.5 Å as molecular area of water are also included in the same table. It is seen, in the first instance, that the net heat of adsorption, E_1-E_L , is of the order of ≈ 2 Kcal/mole which seems to be sufficiently low to rule out possibility of any specific chemical interaction or chemisorption, though not that of hydrogen bonding between water molecule and some of the polar groups.

It was thought of interest to analyse the data also on the basis of Harkins and Jura equation, viz.,

$$\log \frac{p}{p_0} = B - \frac{A}{V^2}$$

where A and B are constants. The plots of $\log p/p_0$ against $1/V^2$ for the various caseins are seen to be linear (Fig. 5), as required by the equation. These workers have shown that the specific surface area (S) of the adsorbent can be obtained from the slope (A) of the linear plot using the expression

$$S = kA^\dagger$$

where k is a constant, the value of which varies with the nature of the adsorbate being 3.83 for water.

Figs. 3 & 4. B.E.T. plots of adsorption isotherms of bovine and buffaloes' caseins respectively.

TABLE 2— V_m , SPECIFIC SURFACE AREA (S), NET HEAT OF ADSORPTION, FREE ENERGY CHANGE AND PARTICLE SIZE FROM WATER ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS

Description of sample	B.E.T. equation		Knee bend		Harkin Jura equation	$(E_1 - E_L)$ Cal/mole	$-\Delta F$ Cal/mole	Particle size Å
	V_m (g/100 g)	S (m ² /g)	V_m (g/100 g)	S (m ² /g)	S (m ² /g)			
<i>Bovine Caseins</i>								
Whole	5.74	202	5.7	200	201	2046	931	223
α -	5.48	192	5.3	186	190	1900	835	236
β -	4.80	168	4.6	161	164	1830	731	268
<i>Buffaloes' Caseins</i>								
Whole	5.60	197	5.5	193	192	1955	895	230
α -	5.40	189	5.1	179	184	1830	810	240
β -	4.70	164	4.4	154	161	1790	703	275

This method of calculating specific surface area has the advantage that it does not require knowledge of molecular area or orientation of adsorbate molecules on the surface of the adsorbent. The values for various bovine and buffaloes' caseins obtained by this method are included in Table 2. The agreement with the corresponding values obtained by B.E.T. equation is seen to be quite close even though the two methods are based on different concepts and postulates.

It is generally believed that the knee of a type II isotherms corresponds to the completion of monolayer. This concept has also been used for calculating specific surface area of solid absorbents. The values of V_m obtained from the amount of adsorption at vapour pressures corresponding to knee of our isotherms, plotted in Figs. 1 and 2, and specific surface areas calculated from them are also included in separate columns of Table 2. It is interesting to note that these values are also in good agreement with those obtained by more intricate calculations based on B.E.T. and Harkins and Jura equations.

Labuza¹⁷ has introduced the term 'water activity', A_w , defined as the ratio of vapour pressure at which monolayer is formed to the saturation vapour pressure at the same temperature. It is evident that the value of A_w in casein and its major fractions lie close

to 0.17 (Fig. 1 and 2). The significance of this term is that any water adsorbed in equilibrium with this

Fig. 5. Harkins and Jura Plots of adsorption isotherms of bovine caseins.

Δ — Δ — Δ Whole casein
 X — X — X α -casein
 O O O β -casein

humidity is tied up or bound to the surface and is not available for microbial activity. In the light of the observation reported in this paper, casein or

its fractions should not be exposed to water vapour at a pressure in excess of 0.17 relative vapour pressure at ordinary temperature.

The close agreement between specific surface area values obtained by three independent methods is highly significant. The value for α -fraction is somewhat higher than that of β -fraction, while the value for whole casein is higher than that of either of its fractions. This is as expected from the respective isotherms of various products.

It was thought of interest to calculate mean diameter (D) of ultimate particles of casein by using well known expression

$$D = \frac{6}{\rho S}$$

where ρ is the density and S is the specific surface area of casein. Taking density of casein and its fractions¹⁸ as 1.34, the mean diameter was found to vary between 223 and 275 Å for various products. It may be noted that the particle size distribution of bovine casein by a method based on electron microscopy has been found to extend between 50 and 1200 Å for a number of different milk samples¹⁹. When mean value is calculated from the frequency of particles of various sizes, the average value of particle diameter comes out to be 290 Å which is very close to our estimates based on surface area measurements. This agreement shows the reliability of specific surface area values as obtained from water isotherms by applying three different postulates. The view held in certain quarters^{1,6,9} that water is sorbed only at specific hydrophilic sites at low relative vapour pressures does not appear to be quite valid. Such sites no doubt correspond to 'active centres', in common adsorbents and water is held more energetically at these sites than elsewhere but when a conventional monolayer is formed it probably covers the entire surface.

It was considered worthwhile to calculate some thermodynamic properties of the adsorbed film. Bull²⁰ used the following equation for calculating integral free energy change, ΔF , for the transfer of water molecules from the vapour state to the surface of proteins and nylon examined by him

$$\Delta F = \int_0^1 n dx \ln x$$

where n is the number of moles of water sorbed per 100 g. protein and x is the relative vapour pressure. Dole and McLaren²¹ using Bull's data for water sorption on a number of proteins and nylon calculated free energy change for the sorption of water between any given vapour pressure range by carrying out the integration between the appropriate limits. They also suggested calculations of free energy change, $\Delta F'$, for the transfer of water molecules from the vapour phase at saturation vapour pressure,

p_0 , to the protein brought to a given vapour pressure, p , by the following relationship derived by them,

$$\Delta F' = \Delta F + nRT \ln x.$$

The values of ΔF and $\Delta F'$ corresponding to the sorption of water vapour at different relative vapour pressures on bovine whole casein are plotted in Fig. 6. It is seen that both the values are identical at the saturation vapour pressure (where $x = 1$), as expected, and are included in Table 2. However, the essential difference between the two sets of values is that whereas the slope of the curve for Dole and McLaren's values decreases abruptly at a certain stage that for the Bull's values remains almost the same in the entire range of vapour pressure. It is interesting to note that the critical relative vapour pressure x at which the slope of the former curve undergoes an abrupt change is close to 0.17, i.e., the vapour pressure at which the monolayer is almost completed. It is also significant to note that the free energy change accompanying the formation of monolayer is quite low which confirms again, that the interactions are rather of weak nature.

The differential heat of adsorption (q_{iso}) was computed from the water isotherms determined at 30° and 40°. The values at increasing surface coverages are plotted in Fig. 7. It is highly significant to note that there is a sudden drop in the value on the approach of the completion of a monolayer. The value at this stage is seen to be fairly close to $E_1 - E_L$, as obtained from the B.E.T. constant C , given in Table 2. Further evidence for the correctness of the monolayer capacity was obtained by calculating differential entropies of adsorption from the following equation

$$q_{iso} = T(S_G - \bar{S}_S)$$

where S_G is the molar entropy of water at temperature T and \bar{S}_S is the differential entropy of the adsorbed phase. Taking molecular entropy of water vapour at 35° as 45.6 cal.degree⁻¹mole⁻¹, it was possible to calculate differential entropies of adsorption. These are plotted against surface coverages in Fig. 8. The values decrease at increasing coverages, as expected, and there is a sudden fall at the stage of formation of the monolayer.

Thus a substantial evidence, based on thermodynamic data, is available for the correctness of the monolayer capacity as obtained from B.E.T. or Harkins and Jura treatment or from the knee of the water isotherm. The data plotted in Fig. 6-8 show clearly that there is an abrupt change in the properties of the adsorbed film at the stage when $V \approx V_m$.

Each isotherm (cf. Fig. 1 and 2) can be split into three parts. The first part which is convex to the sorption axis extends upto approximately 0.17 relative vapour pressure and corresponds to formation of monolayer as already mentioned. The second portion is almost linear and extends upto approximately 0.6 relative vapour pressure. The rate of

Fig. 6. Plot of free energy change against p/p_0 for bovine whole casein. Fig. 7. Plot of differential net heat of adsorption vs. v/V_m for bovine whole casein.

increase in sorption with increase in relative vapour pressure is comparatively less in this region. The amount of water sorbed in second part of the isotherm, however, is almost the same as in the first part and there is virtual completion of the second statistical layer at ~ 0.6 relative vapour pressure. The isotherm beyond 0.6 relative vapour pressure swings vertically upward at a much faster rate indicating rapid formation of multimolecular layers. The number of statistical layers formed at a vapour

Fig. 8. Plot of differential entropy vs. v/V_m for bovine whole casein.

pressure close to saturation vapour pressure ($p/p_0 = 0.95$) is seen to be ~ 4 in each case.

The formation of multimolecular layers on polymers including proteins has been investigated by several workers^{22,13} by applying Frankel, Halsey and Hill (F.H.H.) equation,

$$\log \log (p_0/p) = r \log \frac{v}{V_m}$$

where v is the uptake of water at p/p_0 and r is a constant, the value of which should be 3.0 but has

been found in the case of adsorption of water on anatase²³, polymers²² and proteins¹³ to be close to 2.5. The water isotherms data obtained by us for various caseins are plotted according to this equation in Fig. 9. The relationship is linear in the region of higher relative vapour pressure > 0.6 and the value of r as obtained from the slope, is found to be 2.7, as required. The plots depart from

Fig. 9. F.H.H. plots of bovine caseins.

△-△-△- Whole casein
 X-X-X- α-Casein
 O-O-O- β-Casein

linearity at the stage at which the relative vapour pressure corresponds to ≈ 0.6 . Since the F.H.H. equation is valid only for multilayer adsorption, the transition from the curved nature of the isotherm to linear portion where p/p_0 approaches 0.6 gives distinct indication for formation of multimolecular layers at higher r.v.p's. The water adsorbed in this region may not be held so firmly. This view was

checked by measuring freezing points of water adsorbed at different relative vapour pressures by one of the unfractionated caseins, by following the technique based on vapour pressure measurements²⁴. The results are recorded in Table 3. It is seen that water sorbed at a relative vapour pressure > 0.6 freezes at temperatures only slightly below the normal freezing point while that sorbed at 0.6

TABLE 3—FREEZING POINT OF WATER ADSORBED ON BOVINE WHOLE CASEIN AT DIFFERENT RELATIVE VAPOUR PRESSURES

Relative vapour pressure	Freezing Point (°C)
0.989	-0.1
0.951	-0.3
0.914	-0.9
0.865	-1.3
0.840	-2.7
0.755	-2.9
0.689	-4.2
0.612	< -40

relative vapour pressure does not freeze even at -40° . Berlin *et al.*²⁵ are of the view that any water held in proteins which does not freeze at -40° may be taken as bound or held tightly to the surface. It may be concluded, therefore, that water sorbed in the first two regions of the isotherms (Fig. 1 and 2) is held much more firmly than that sorbed in the third region of the isotherm. The exposure of casein to water vapour at relative vapour pressure > 0.6 is likely to result in rapid denaturation of casein.

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